

Survey on Network analysis data on emotional intelligence, stress coping strategies and anxiety symptoms in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic in Peruvian police

* Required

BRIEF COPE

Take note that 1 = Strongly Agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Strongly Disagree, and 4 = Disagree.

I'm trying to get someone to help me or advise on what to do. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I concentrate my efforts on doing something about the situation I'm in. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I accept the reality of what has happened. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I resort to work or other activities to take my mind off things. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I tell myself "this isn't real." *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I try to propose a strategy about what do. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I make jokes about it. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I criticize myself. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I get emotional support from others. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I take steps to try to make the situation better. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I give up trying to take care of it. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I say things to vent my unpleasant feelings. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I refuse to believe that it happened. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I try to see it with different eyes, to make it seem more positive. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I use alcohol or other drugs to make myself feel better. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I try to find comfort in my religion or spiritual beliefs. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I get comfort and understanding from someone. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I look for something good in what is happening. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I laugh at the situation. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I pray or meditate. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I learn to live with it. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I do something to think less about it, such as like going to the movies or watching TV. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I express my negative feelings. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I use alcohol or other drugs to help me get through it. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I give up trying to cope with problem. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I think carefully about the steps to go on. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

I blame myself for what has happened. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I get other people to help me or advise. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

WLEIS INTELLIGENCE EMOTIONAL

Take note that 1 = Strongly Agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Strongly Disagree, and 4 = Disagree.

La mayoría de las veces sé distinguir porqué tengo ciertos sentimientos [I have a good sense of why I have certain feelings most of the time] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

Tengo una buena comprensión de mis propias emociones [I have good understanding of my own emotions] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Realmente comprendo lo que yo siento [I really understand what I feel] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Siempre sé si estoy o no estoy feliz [I always know whether or not I am happy]
Evaluación de las emociones de los demás [Other 's Emotion Appraisal, OEA] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

Conozco siempre las emociones de mis amigos a través de sus comportamientos [I always know my friends' emotions from their behaviour] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Soy un buen observador de las emociones de los demás [I am a good observer of others' emotions] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Soy sensible a los sentimientos y emociones de los demás [I am sensitive to the feelings and emotions of others] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

Tengo una buena comprensión de las emociones de las personas que me rodean
[I have good understanding of the emotions of people around me] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Siempre me fi jo metas y luego intento hacerlo lo mejor para alcanzarlas [I always
set goals for myself and then try my best to achieve them] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Siempre me digo a mi mismo que soy una persona competente [I always tell
myself I am a competent person] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

Soy una persona auto-motivadora [I am a self-motivating person] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Siempre me animo a mi mismo para hacerlo lo mejor que pueda [I would always encourage myself to try my best] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Soy capaz de controlar mi temperamento y manejar las dificultades de manera racional [I am able to control my temper so that I can handle difficulties rationally] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

Soy capaz de controlar mis propias emociones [I am quite capable of controlling my own emotions] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Me puedo calmar fácilmente cuando me siento enfadado [I can always calm down quickly when I am very angry] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Tengo un buen control de mis propias emociones [I have good control of my own emotions] *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Get link

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"

Google Forms

Pre-fill responses, then click "Get link"